

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

ISSN: 2992-8902

74-91 XALQARO DARAJA

MAXSUS SON, 2024

IJTIMOIY, IQTISODIY, SIYOSIY, ILMIY, OMMABOP JURNAL

2024-YIL 18-19-APREL

**“RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA AGROIQTISODIYOT VA
BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI VA
ULARNING YECHIMLARI” PROFESSOR NURILLA SULAYMONOVICH
SANAYEV TAVALLUDINING 85 YILLIGIGA BAG’ISHLANGAN**

XALQARO ILMIY-AMALIY KONFERENSIYA

SAMARQAND DAVLAT VETERINARIYA MEDITSINASI,
CHORVACHILIK VA BIOTEXNOLOGIYALAR UNIVERSITETI, 2024

Yashil **IQTISODIYOT** va **TARAQQIYOT**

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Elektron nashr. 678 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 19-aprel kuni ruxsat etildi.

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, t.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, i.f.d., O'zR Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vaziri o'rinbosari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, i.f.d., prof., O'zR Oliy Majlisi qonunchilik palatasi deputati
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich i.f.n., professor, MIM akademiyasi rektori
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, i.f.d., prof., TDIU YoMMMIB birinchi prorektori
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalendarovna, i.f.d., prof., TDIU Ilmiy ishlar va innovatsiyalar bo'yicha prorektori
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, i.f.d., prof., "O'IRIAM" ilmiy tadqiqot markazi direktori – prorektor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, i.f.d., TMI professori
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, i.f.n., TDIU professori
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, t.f.d., Rossiya xalqlar do'stligi universiteti professori
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, i.f.d., prof., Xalqaro "Nordik" universiteti rektori
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, f.f.d., TDIU professori
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, i.f.d. TDIU professori
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, t.f.d., professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, i.f.d., TDIU professori
Musyeva Shoira Azimovna, SamDu IS instituti professori
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, i.f.f.d., "El-yurt umidi" jamg'armasi ijrochi direktori o'rinbosari
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, t.f.f.d., TAQU katta o'qituvchisi
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, i. f. n., TDAU dotsenti
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, i.f.f.d., TDIU dotsenti
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, f.f.n., Farg'ona davlat universiteti dotsenti
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, i.f.f.d. (PhD), Alfraganus universiteti dotsenti
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, PhD, Turkiya Anqara universiteti doktoranti
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Maxamatjon o'g'li, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farxod, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi iqtisodiy jinoyatlarga qarshi kurashish departamenti bo'limi boshlig'i
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, i.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, i.f.f.d, TDIU dotsenti
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, i.f.d., TMI dotsenti
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, TDIU mustaqil tadqiqotchisi

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

MUNDARIJA

Benazir ustozni yod etib	10
Samarqand davlat veterinariya meditsinasi, chorvachilik va biotexnologiyalar universiteti jamoasi	
Qishloq xo'jaligi taraqqiyotining ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	12
Yunusov Xudaynazar Beknazarovich	
Agroklasterlarda biznes jarayonlari moliyaviy natijalari hisobini takomillashtirish	14
Alikulov Abdimo'min, Koshkaldal Irina	
Assessment of the ESG rating of banks.....	19
Ruziyeva Elvira, Eshmuradov Ulugbek	
Contract Preferences of Smallholders: Evidence From a Study on Potato Production in Uzbekistan	24
Sanaev Golib, Sanaeva Rakhima, Nurullaev Ulmasjon, Nurullaeva Bakhora, Sanaev Anvar	
Taxation Systems in the Agricultural Production Sphere in the Context of Resistance to Shadow Economy	34
Koshkaldal Iryna, Dombrovska Olena, Alikulov Abdimumin	
Factors Influencing Farmers' Cooperation in Irrigation: A Study of Samarkand Province, Uzbekistan	39
Tadjiev Abdusame Abduxamidovich	
Xalqaro standartlar asosida qishloq xo'jaligida kapital qo'yilmalar hisobi hamda hisobotlarini takomillashtirish.....	43
Xasanov Baxodir Akramovich, Egamberdiyeva Salima Rayimovna, Raxmatov Jonibek Ismoil o'g'li	
Tijorat banklarida ichki auditida muhimlik va auditor riski masalalari.....	50
Ibragimov Abdugapur Karimovich, Qo'ldoshev Dilshod Melixurozovich	
Agroklasterlar ichki sotish jarayonida transfert baholarni belgilashni tashkiliy-uslubiy jihatlarini	57
Eshmuradov Ulug'bek Tashmuratovich	
Auditda regression tahlilni qo'llashning xususiyatlari	64
Tajekeev Ziyatdin Kobeyinovich	
Uzumchilik fermer xo'jaliklarida ishlab chiqarish xarajatlari hisobini takomillashtirish.....	67
Ibragimov Mansur Mardonovich	
Xalqaro standartlar asosida qishloq xo'jaligida aktivlarni tasniflash, ularning hisobi va hisobotini takomillashtirish.....	71
Egamberdiyeva Salima Rayimovna	
The Place of Digitalisation in the Rural Areas Development of Ukraine.....	76
Riasnianska A. M., Kniaz O. V.	
Yalpi ichki va hududiy mahsulotning ko'payishida faol tadbirkorlikning o'rni	79
Salamov Ibroxim, Kudratov Rizo Turdibayevich, Nazarova Maryam Sharipovna	
Inflyatsion targetlash rejimining pul-kredit siyosatini amalga oshirishdagi ahamiyati	84
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich	
Asalarichilikning qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyotidagi o'rni va uni rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	89
Alikulov Abdimo'min Ismatovich, Ishturdiyev Hasan Abdigapparovich	
Uzumchilik majmuining tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmi va uning tamoyillari.....	94
Boltayev Nazarbek Narzullayevich	
Mintaqaviy klasterning xususiyatlari.....	98
Urdushev Hamrakul	
Considerations for Bolstering Entrepreneurship in the Evolution of the Domestic Economy	102
Shadiyeva Gulnora Mardiyevna	
Chorvachilik tarmog'ida ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish imkoniyatlari.....	107
Kudratov Rizo Turdibayevich, O'roqov Feruz Ibodullayevich	
Oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashda qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari yetishtirishning hududiy jihatlarini	112
Kazakova Zulayho Salaxiddinovna, Nazarova Maryam Sharipovna	

Yalpi ichki mahsulot va uni hisoblashni takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	117
Xalmurzaev Mansur, Abdushukurov Xondamir	
Qishloq xo'jaligi korxonalarida tovar-moddiy qiymatliklar hisobini takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	122
Raximova Umida Rabbimovna	
Mamlakatimiz agrar tarmog'ida innovatsiyalarga asoslangan tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish.....	127
Olimova Nodira hamrakulovna	
Banklarda ichki auditni xalqaro audit standartlari asosida takomillashtirish.....	131
Rizayev Nurbek Qodirovich, Boymatova Chinora Ilxomovna	
Agroklastarlarda asosiy vositalarni modernizatsiyalash va ta'mirlash xarajatlari hisobini takomillashtirish.....	137
Alikulov Abdimo'min Ismatovich, Ibodullaev D., Abdushukurov Xondamir Botiraliyevich	
Davlat budjetida boshqaruv xarajatlarini moliyalashtirishni takomillashtirish yo'llari va xarajatlarning optimallashtiruv muammolari.....	142
Narziyeva Guzal Baxtiyorovna	
Bandlikni ta'minlash va kambag'allikni qisqartirishni yuzaga keltiruvchi sabablar hamda ularning yechimi.....	146
Ahmatova Qunduzbonu Asliddinovna, Sunnatullayev Musurmon Sunnatullo o'g'li, Salamov Ibroxim	
Global iqtisodiy rivojlanish sharoitida yashil iqtisodiyot muammolari.....	151
Tirkashev Farhod Mahmudovich, Musurmonov Nodirbek Ahmadovich	
Menejer boshqaruvida boshqaruv mehnati va guruhlar dinamikasi.....	155
Xasanova Sitara Islamovna	
G'allachilik klasterlarida buxgalteriya hisobi shakllarini takomillashtirish.....	158
Yuldashev Sherali Xaitovich	
Современность услуг агропромышленного комплекса в условиях инновационной экономики положение дел.....	163
Тураев Баходир Хатамович, Рузиев Хамрокул Жураевич	
Влияние внешних факторов на эффективность производства животноводства.....	170
Хамдамова Насиба Аблакуловна	
Banklarda ichki auditni rejalashtirish masalalari.....	173
Ibragimova Iroda Rashid qizi, Safarov Abdumajit Abdixamidovich	
The Importance of Digital Technologies in the Development of Agriculture.....	179
Rabbimov Elbek Abdulloevich	
Yakka tartibdagi tadbirkorlarni soliqqa tortish o'zini o'zi band qilishni davlat tomonidan tartibga solish shakli sifatida.....	182
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna, Javmanov Jamshed Abdusamatovich	
O'zbekiston pensiya tizimida pensiya hisoblash va to'lashni rivojlantirishda xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasini uyg'unlashtirish.....	186
Xasanov Baxodir Akramovich, Nurmanov Din-Axmed Tileubayevich	
Uzumchilik mahsulotlari eksportini oshirish omillari.....	193
Ibragimov Mansur Mardonovich	
Korxonalarining xo'jalik faoliyati hisobining mohiyati, ahamiyati va hisob turlari.....	196
Ishturdiyev Hasan Abdigapparovich, Tilabov Shohruh Baxriddin o'g'li, Irisboyev Raxmatilla Shavkat o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotning o'zbekistondagi holati va uning rivojlanish istiqbollari.....	200
Kazakova Zulayho Salaxiddinovna, Abdullayev Sanjar Sayfiddin o'g'li, Sunnatullayev Musurmon Sunnatulla o'g'li	
Fermer xo'jaliklar faoliyatida investitsiyalarning o'rni.....	204
Nomozova Mahliyo Mampirjon qizi, Yuldashev Muhammad Utkir o'g'li, Solijonova Diyora Xaydarali qizi, Saydullayev Akbarali Akram o'g'li, Urazov Jamshidjon Sa'dullayevich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotning o'rni va joriy etishdagi imkoniyatlari.....	209
Salamov Ibroxim, Javmanov Jamshed Abdusamatovich, Ummatov Begzod Ikrom ugli, Bekpolatov Sul-tonxon Sherzod ugli	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida asosiy vositalarni hisobga olishni takomillashtirish.....	214
Xatamov Kobil Xayrievich, Sodiqov Xayrulla Sattorovich	
Improving Cost Accounting for Sales of Agricultural Products in Farms.....	218
Abdimumin Alikulov, Ulugbek Eshmuradov, Khondamir Abdushukurov	

Servis korxonalarini raqamli iqtisodiyotga o'tkazishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish	224
Kurbanova Raxima Jamshedovna	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotning bugungi kundagi holati.....	228
Nurmanov Sherzod Xujayarovich, Eshimova Gulandom Botir qizi, Daniyarov Xurshid Baxtiyarovich	
Qoramolchilikda ozuqa ta'minotini yaxshilash yo'llari	233
Nurullayev Ulug'bek Uytalovich, Urazov Jamshidjon Sa'dullayevich	
Meva-sabzavotchilik klasterlarida faol tadbirkorlikning iqtisodiy samaradorlikni oshirishdagi o'rni	236
Ibroxim Salomov, Roziyeva Gulxayo Chorievna	
Qishloq xo'jaligini rivojlantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	242
Tirkashev Farhod Mahmudovich, Isaxonov Shaxzodjon Nurali o'g'li	
O'zbekiston chorvachiligidagi muammolar va ularning yechimi.....	246
Xudoyberdiyeva Marifat Umarovna, Xamdamova Nasiba Ablakulovna, Esirgapov Diyor Akramovich, Ulmasov Tohir Suvonqulovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirishda raqamli texnologiyalarning o'rni va ahamiyati	249
Kazakova Zulayho Salaxiddinovna, Ulmasov Amirxon Rasul o'g'li, Botirov Bekzod Ulug'bek o'g'li	
Механизмы и инструменты финансирования малых и средних сельскохозяйственных предприятий (На примере Центральноазиатского региона).....	253
Худойбердиева Асила	
Agroklasterlarda kapital qo'yilmalar hisobini xalqaro standartlar asosida takomillashtirish masalalari.....	259
Irisboev Rahmatillo Shavkat o'g'li, Jo'rayeva Diyora Olimjonovna, Eshmuradov Ulug'bek Tashmuratovich	
Milliy iqtisodiyotda kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rolini oshirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari	265
Saidxonov Akmalxon	
Improving Accounting and Auditing of Inventories in Agricultural Clusters	269
Raximova Umida Rabbimovna	
Maishiy xizmatlar sohasining rivojlanish tendensiyalari va kambag'allikni qisqartirishdagi o'rni.....	272
Rajabov Navruzbek Azimjonovich	
Chorvachilik tarmog'ida mahsulotlarni qayta ishlash samaradorligini oshirish imkoniytlari	277
Salomov Ibroxim, Nurmanov Sherzod Xujayarovich, Hotamov Adhamjon Asqarjon o'g'li	
Порядок применения и актуальность международных стандартов финансовой отчетности в деятельности коммерческих банков и предприятий	282
Нарзиева Гузал Бахтиёровна, Хомидов Асилбек Отабек угли, Асомиддинов Хусан Асомиддин угли, Болтабаев Диёрбек Омандурди угли	
Savdo korxonalarida segmentar hisobning o'rni va ahamiyati	286
Mardonov Mamed Shavkatovich, Bobomuradova Sarvinov Ziyadullayevna	
Livestock Development Problems and Prospects in Uzbekistan	289
Khamdamova Nasiba Ablakulovna, Ulmasova Oyul Bakhtiyarovna, Xudayberdiyeva Marifat Umarovna	
Понятие и учет капитальных вложений в агрокластерах.....	292
Жураева Диёра Олимджановна	
Xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarini innovatsion modernizatsiyalashda iqtisodiy samaradorlikni hisoblash metodini takomillashtirish	297
Kurbanova Raxima Jamshedovna, Umurzoqova Sevinch Karim qizi	
Tarmoq mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarish va sotishda innovatsion texnologiyalarni qo'llashning iqtisodiy samaradorligi	301
Nazarova Maryam Sharipovna, Kazakova Zulayho Salaxiddinovna	
Maishiy xizmatlar sohasini tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlarini takomillashtirishda raqamli innovatsion texnologiyalarning roli va ahamiyati	304
Quliyev Begimqul Melikovich	
O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotining rivojlanishi va iqtisodiy o'sish uchun barqaror investitsiya muhitini ta'minlash masalalari.....	308
Raximova Umida Rabbimovna, Elmurodova Dilnoza Farxodovna	

Biznesni qo'llab-quvvatlashda iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy holatni yaxshilash imkoniyatlari	311
Salamov Ibroxim, Janibekov Faxriddin Beknazarovich, Ulmasova Oygul Baxtiyorovna, Xudayberdiyeva Marifat Umarovna	
G'alla urug'chiligida boshlang'ich hisob va ichki nazoratni takomillashtirish	315
Yuldashev Sherali Xaitovich, Yusupov Uchqun, Zokirov Behruz	
Baliqchilik xo'jaliklarini rejalashtirishning ahamiyati va bosqichlari.....	318
Dosmuratova Shaxista Kengashovna	
"Yashil" iqtisodiyot: konsepsiyaning shakllanishi va asosiy kategoriyalari.....	321
Tirkashev Farhod Mahmudovich, Toshpulatova Kamola Xurshed qizi	
Sutchilik yo'nalishidagi xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar faoliyatida marketing elementlaridan foydalanish	324
Urazov Jamshidjon Sa'dullayevich	
Biznes jarayonlarida "xarajat" va "tannarx" kategoriyalarining nazariy jihatlari.....	328
Xondamir Abdushukurov, Ulug'bek Eshmuradov	
Перспективы развития бухгалтерского учета и аудита на основе международных стандартов.....	333
Рахимова Умида Раббимовна, Асомиддинов Хусан Асомиддин угли, Болтабаев Диёрбек Омондурди угли, Хомидов Аслбек Отабек угли	
Asosiy vositalarni hisobga olishning xalqaro va milliy standartlarda aks ettirishning farqli jihatlari	336
Xatamov Kobil Xayrievich, Turabaeva Ozoda Ilxambekovna	
Qishloq hududlarida ekoturizm maskanlarining turistik salohiyati va sig'imi tahlili.....	340
Abduraxmanova Aqida Fayzulla qizi, Xoshimova Sevara Bahromovna, Sayfullaev Umidulla Fazliddin o'g'li	
Chorvachilik tarmoqlarida otchilik infratuzilmasining hozirgi holati va istiqboldagi iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish imkoniyatlari	346
Salamov Ibroxim, Nurmanov Sherzod Xujayarovich, Tursunov Alpomish Amanovich, Yo'ldoshev Raxim Nuriddin o'g'li	
Qishloq xo'jaligi klasterlari va fermer xo'jaliklari faoliyatida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari	351
Nasimjon Babayev, Dilorom Yorbekova, Umidullo Fayzullayev	
Agroklasterlarda biznes jarayonlari sotish hisobini takomillashtirish	354
Abdunazarova Sevinch, Aliqulova Zebuniso, Eshmuradov Ulug'bek Tashmuratovich	
Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida qishloq xo'jalik ishlab chiqarishining samaradorligi	360
Kudratov Rizo Turdibayevich, Abduxaliqova Farangiz Abduxoliq qizi	
Increasing Efficiency of Catering Enterprises Through Modernization.....	365
Kurbanova Rakhima Jamshedovna	
Chorvachilik majmuasi infratuzilmasi va uni rivojlantirish	369
Nurmanov Sherzod Xujayarovich, Aslonov Xotamjon Sharibboy o'g'li	
Davlat-xususiy sherikchiligini rivojlantirishda klasterlarning ahamiyati	373
Tirkashev Farhod Mahmudovich, Raxmatullayev Sherzod Mexriddinovich	
Studying the Features of Innovative Development in The Agricultural Sector of the Economy.....	377
Yorbekova Dilorom Muxammadkulovna	
Chorvachilikda klasterlashning ayrim masalalari	380
Urdushev Hamrakul, Mavlyanov Majid Tuychiyevich	
Issues of Development of "Green Economy" in the Context of the Actualization of the Problem of Ecology and Climate Change.....	385
Mukhayyo Dustova	
Xizmatlar sohasi rivojlanishining aholi turmush darajasiga ta'siri.....	390
Xudoyberdiyeva Marifat Umarovna	
Baliqchilik xo'jaliklarini rivojlantirish prognozini ishlab chiqish masalalari	393
Dosmuratova Shaxista Kengashovna	
Mahalliy soliqlar va mahalliy yig'imlarning iqtisodiy mohiyati.....	396
Tirkashev Farhod Mahmudovich, Asomiddinov Husan Asomiddin o'g'li	
Turizm korxonalarini hisob siyosatini shakllantirish	400
Ibragimov Mansur Mardonovich	

Korxonalarda moliyaviy holatini ifodalovchi ko'rsatkichlar tahlili	404
Ishturdiyev Hasan Abdigapparovich, Tilabov Shohruh Baxriddin o'g'li, Yusupova Ergashoy	
Innovatsiya, innovatsion iqtisodiyot atamalarining mohiyati va ulardan samarali foydalanish yo'llari.....	408
Xudoyberdiyeva Marifat Umarovna, Boyjigitov Kamronmirzo Sobirjon o'g'li, Obloberdiyev Shuxrat Sharof o'g'li	
The Processing Indicators of Livestock Products on the Basis of Economic Statistical Models.....	411
Yorbekova Dilrom Muxammadkulovna, Hotamov Adhamjon Asqarjon o'g'li	
Paxta-to'qimachilik klasterlarida tola ishlab chiqarish xarajatlari tahlili	414
Alikulov Abdimo'min Ismatovich, Farangiz Rustamova	
Meva-sabzavotchilikni rivojlantirishda klaster yondashuvining afzalliklari	419
Eshankulov Sirojiddin Xakimovich	
Prospects for Leaving the Population Out of Poverty	424
Javmanov Jamshed Abdusamatovich, Radjabov Navruzbek Azimjonovich, Uralov Baxtiyor Maxmudovich, Fayzullayev Umidullo Xayrullo o'g'li	
Tijorat banklarida korrupsiyaga qarshi kurashishning kompayens nazorati usullarini takomillashtirish.....	429
Sultanov Abrorbek Umarali o'g'li, Axmedov Shuxrat Xikmatullayevich	
Segmentar va moliyaviy hisobot tuzishda xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar mulkini baholashning metodologik muammolari	435
G'olibjon Alikulov	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotga o'tish orqali yashirin iqtisodiyotni jamiyatga ta'sirini kamaytirish	439
Uralov Baxtiyor Maxmudovich, Abdusalomov Farruh G'ayrat o'g'li	
Sustainable Farming Futures: the Economic Need of Climate Change Program in Uzbekistan.....	443
Akhmadjon Nurullaev, Sanayeva Raxima Amirqulovna, Visola Khasanova, Bakhora Nurullaeva, Anvar Sanaev	
Problems and Prospects of Cadastral Valuation of Land Resources in the Republic of Kazakhstan	447
Berdimurat Nazimgul, Bassybekova Zh.B.	
Значение цифровизации в сельском хозяйстве	451
Сыздықова Азиза Оралбайқызы, Сапарова Айнура Алпамысовна	
Xizmatlar sohasi samaradorligini oshirish masalalari	456
Mirzayev Qulmamat Jonuzakovich, Mardanova Mohidil Otabek qizi, Mirzayev Azzamjon Jonuzokovich	
Aholini o'z-o'zini bandlikka jalb qilish orqali ishsizlik darajasini pasaytirish.....	461
Javmanov Jamshed Abdusamatovich, Jo'rayev Sherali Anor o'g'li	
Innovatsiyani joriy qilishning fermer xo'jaliklari daromadlariga ta'siri	465
Eshboyev Diyorbek Yo'ldosh o'g'li, Sinayev Sherali Islom o'g'li, Ismoyilov Azamat Isroyilovich	
Moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlariga muvofiq daromadni tan olish masalalari.....	471
Kozimjonov Abrorbek	
O'zbekistonda kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishda raqamli texnologiyalarning yutuqlari va muammolari.....	475
Ochilova Mohigul Toshtemir qizi	
Soliq ma'murchiligida raqamli iqtisodiyotning ahamiyati va uning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari tahlili	479
Uralov Baxtiyor Maxmudovich, Javmanov Jamshed Abdusamatovich, Holmirzayev Sardor Ravshan o'g'li, Tursinaliyev Abdulaziz Shokirjon o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda davlat xizmatlari ko'rsatish milliy tizimini rivojlanishi: xronologik tahlil.....	484
Hasanov Habibullo	
Chorvachilikning mamlakat iqtisodiyotidagi ahamiyati va uning rivojlanishi	488
Xamdamova Nasiba Ablakulovna, Tirkashev Farxod Mahmudovich, Sayfullayev Akbar Xoljigit o'g'li, Erkinov Samandar Maxmudovich	
O'zbekiston chorvachiligiga oid FAO ma'lumotlari haqida	493
Pardayeva Kamola	
Moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlariga muvofiq xaridorlar bilan tuziladigan shartnomalar asosida tushumni hisobga olishning ahamiyati	498
Norbekov Davron	
Paxtachilik klasterlarida ishlab chiqarishga ta'sir etuvchi omillarning tahlili	502
Javmanov Jamshed Abdusamatovich, Abduraxmonov Orifbek Odiljon o'g'li	

Raqamli iqtisodiyotning zamonamizdagi bugungi o'rnini	506
Tirkashev Farhod Mahmudovich, Zarmaxmatov Nomozjon Baxodir o'g'li	
Improving Cost Audit in Innovation Activities	510
Mustafoev is the son of Akbar Mustafa	
Konsolidatsiyalashgan moliyaviy hisobotni mxs asosida transformatsiya qilish zaruriyati	514
Xolmurodov Otabek	
Klasterlarni tashkil etishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlari va ularning mamlakat iqtisodiyotida tutgan o'rnini	521
Javmanov Jamshed Abdusamatovich, Homidov Aslbek Otabek o'g'li, Asomiddinov Husan Asomiddin o'g'li, Boltayev Diyorbek Omondurdi o'g'li	
Soliq imtiyozlarini nazariy asoslash va huquqiy tartibga solish	526
Uralov Baxtiyor Maxmudovich	
Sug'urta shartnomalari va sug'urta majburiyatlari hisobini moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlari asosida takomillashtirish	531
Ochilov Ilyos Keldiyorovich	
Обеспечение привлекательности инвестиции коммерческих банков	537
Назаров Килич Холмурадович, Нафасов Шохрухбек Хошимович	
O'zbekistonda tashqi savdoning rivojlanishi va muammolari	539
Xudayberdiyev U.	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida mehnatga haq to'lashning nazariy jihatdan tashkiliy-iqtisodiy asoslari	542
Rajabov Navruzbek Azimjonovich, Toshmurodova Dilbar Muzaffar qizi	
Human Capital in Education	546
Ibragimov Mansur Mardonovich, Ergashev Olloyor	
Qishloq joylarida xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini rivojlantirish hamda o'zini o'zi band qilish orqali ishsizlikni kamaytirishning nazariy asoslari	551
Jo'rayev Sherali Anor o'g'li, Abdikarimov Nazirbek Odil o'g'li, Uralov Baxtiyor Maxmudovich	
Uchqora uzumi-mayizini yetishtirishning iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish imkoniyatlari	555
Salamov Ibroxim, Kudratov Rizo Turdibayevich, Janibekov Faxriddin Beknazarovich	
Moliyaviy natijalarning tavsifini takomillashtirish	561
Yusupova Farizabonu Zarifovna	
Kambag'allik va uni qisqartirish yo'llari	564
Tirkashev Farhod Mahmudovich, Do'stiyov Mirabbos Erkin o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida aholi turmush darajasini oshirishda xizmat ko'rsatish sohasining ahamiyati	568
Xolmurodov Otabek	
O'zbekistonda aholi turmush darajasi va daromadlarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	570
Rajabov Navruzbek Azimjonovich, Uralov Baxtiyor Maxmudovich, Saidmurodov Sardor Mirsalohovich	
SWOT-анализ конкурентоспособности национального туризма в Узбекистане в условиях преодоления последствий пандемии	574
Ochilova Mohigul Toshtemir qizi, Abduzoirov Sarvarbek	
Ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirish va aholi turmush darajasini yanada yaxshilashda iqtisodiy samaradorlikni oshirishning ahamiyati	577
Salamov Ibroxim, Kudratov Rizo Turdibayevich, hamdamova Nasiba Ablakulovna	
Jahon iqtisodiyoti va xalqaro savdo munosabatlari	582
Tirkashev Farhod Mahmudovich, Xo'jaqulov Inomjon Rustam o'g'li	
Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitiga mos rivojlantirishning ayrim masalalari	586
Mirzayev Qulmamat Jonuzakovich, Sherzodova Diyora Sherzod qizi	
Turistik destinatsiyalarni rivojlantirish orqali turistik zonalarni takomillashtirish	589
Raxmonov Siyovush Turob ug'li, Ochilova Mohigul Toshtemir qizi	
Ivermektin, klozantel, iversantapulus dori vositalarining marketing tahlili	592
Raxmadullayev Humoyun Rashid o'g'li, Farmonov Nizom, Salamov Ibroxim	
Цифровая оптимизация для экологической безопасности в агропромышленном комплексе	597
Юнусов Худайназар Бекназарович, Сафарова Лола Улмасовна	

Смысловой – системный анализ процессов обработки плодов и овощей энергии начального импульса.....	602
Курбанов Жамшед Маджидович, Курбонова Мадина Жамшедовна	
Формирования алгоритма расчета эффективности транспортно-логистической системы поставок грузов.....	605
Кубаев Улугбек	
Роль и потенциал севооборота в создании устойчивых и экологически чистых систем в сельском хозяйстве на основе цифровизации	611
Юнусов Худайназар Бекназарович, Сафарова Лола Улмасовна	
Qoramollar uchun ozuqa ratsionini tuzishda innovatsion yondashuv	617
Mavlyanov Majid Tuychiyevich	
Landshaft bog'dorchilikni rivojlantirishda autocad dasturining o'rnini.....	624
Ravshanov Sanjar Tolibjonovich, Sulaymonov Mirobid Abduxolikovich	
Aniq qishloq xo'jaligida o'zgaruvchan me'yorlarni qo'llash.....	628
Akbarov Husan O'zbekxonovich, Bekzod Quدراتov	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotda neyron tarmoqlaridan foydalanishning ahamiyati.....	634
Otoboyeva Aziza Shakirovna	
Iqtisodiy masalalarni tahlil qilish, me'yorlash, rejalashtirish, baholash hamda bashorat qilishda korrelyatsiya va regressiya usuli.....	637
Aktamova Vasila Uktamovna, Axtamova Umida O'ktam qizi	
Iqtisodiy ekonometrik modelni tuzish hamda avtokorrelyatsiya mavjudligini aniqlash	641
Raximov Abdulaxad Nematovich	
O'zbekistonda qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini yetishtirishda agrovoltaika texnologiyasini qo'llash istiqbollari	646
Berdiyev G'ayrat Ibragimovich, Eshpulatov Dostonbek Baxodir o'g'li, Malikova Sevinch Telman qizi	
Развитие системы цифровизации в сельском хозяйстве и в народной медицине	650
Рахмонов Фариз Зафаржонович, Мухиддинова Сабрина Мунисовна, Усманова Лайло Рахматуллаевна, Рахмонова Хабиба Нуруллаевна	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot fanlarini o'qitishda zamonaviy pedagogik metodlar va virtual onlayn kurslardan foydalanish.....	653
Sulaymonov Mirobid Abduxolikovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligini boshqarishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning afzalliklari	656
Ravshanov Sanjar Tolibjonovich	
Ekin maydonlari tuproqlarini tahlil qilish va boshqarishda sun'iy intellekt tizimlaridan foydalanishning o'rnini.....	660
Otoboyeva Aziza Shakirovna, Artikov Farxod Sayfiddinovich, Usanov Yoqub Dilmurod o'g'li	
О некоторых нестандартных способах решения иррациональных уравнений	664
Актамова Васи́ла Уктамовна	
Корхоналарни тугатишнинг норматив ва ташкилий-услугий таъминотини такомиллаштириш	666
Дусмуратов Раджапбай Давлатбаевич	
Юридик шахсларни тугатишнинг норматив-ҳуқуқий таъминоти.....	670
Давлетов Икрам Рахимберганович	
Саноат корхоналарида мулкрий муносабатларни тартибга солишнинг илмий назарий асослари.....	674
Бобобеков Эргаш Абдумаликович	

IMPROVING ACCOUNTING AND AUDITING OF INVENTORIES IN AGRICULTURAL CLUSTERS

Raximova Umida Rabbimovna

Researcher of Samarkand State University veterinary medicine,
livestock and biotechnologies

Abstract: Currently, in a market economy, the procurement and acquisition of inventories is of great importance at the initial stage of procurement. To achieve the goal of proper procurement and consumption of inventory, with further rational use, the accounting service must contain complete, transparent information that allows monthly analysis of actions for the procurement and acquisition of inventory. In addition, accounting data must contain information to find reserves for reducing production costs in terms of rational acquisition of inventory items. The analysis of this article is of great importance for effective financial management. Inventories can constitute a significant share not only of current assets, but also of the enterprise's assets in general. This may indicate that enterprises are experiencing difficulties with the sale of products, violations of production technology and the choice of ineffective sales methods.

Key words: materiality, policies, financial statements, omission, misrepresentation, economic decisions, materiality, credibility, material error, users.

Annotatsiya: Hozirgi vaqtda bozor iqtisodiyoti sharoitida tovar-moddiy zaxiralarni xarid qilish va sotib olish xaridning dastlabki bosqichida katta ahamiyatga ega. Tovar-moddiy boyliklarni to'g'ri sotib olish va iste'mol qilish maqsadiga erishish uchun undan oqilona foydalanish uchun buxgalteriya xizmati to'liq, shaffof ma'lumotlarni o'z ichiga olishi kerak, bu esa o'z o'rnida tovar-moddiy boyliklarini xarid qilish va sotib olish bo'yicha harakatlarni oylik tahlil qilish imkonini beradi. Bundan tashqari, buxgalteriya hisobi ma'lumotlari inventarlarni oqilona sotib olish nuqtayi nazaridan ishlab chiqarish xarajatlarini kamaytirish uchun zaxiralarni topish uchun ma'lumotlarni o'z ichiga olishi kerak. Ushbu maqola tahlili samarali moliyaviy boshqaruv uchun katta ahamiyatga ega. Tovar-moddiy zaxiralar nafaqat aylanma mablag'larning, balki umuman korxonalarining muhim qismini tashkil qilishi mumkin. Bu korxonalarda mahsulotlarni sotishda qiyinchiliklar, ishlab chiqarish texnologiyasining buzilishi va samarasiz sotish usullarini tanlashda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelayotganligini ko'rsatishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: mohiyat, siyosat, moliyaviy hisobot, qoldirib ketish, noto'g'ri taqdimot, iqtisodiy qarorlar, muhimlik, ishonchlilik, jiddiy xatolar, foydalanuvchilar.

Аннотация: В настоящее время в условиях рыночной экономики большое значение на начальном этапе закупок имеет закупка и приобретение ТМЦ. Для достижения цели правильной заготовки и потребления ТМЦ, с дальнейшим их рациональным использованием, бухгалтерская служба должна содержать полную, прозрачную информацию, позволяющую ежемесячно анализировать действия по заготовке и приобретению ТМЦ. Кроме того, данные бухгалтерского учета должны содержать информацию для поиска резервов снижения себестоимости продукции в части рационального приобретения товарно-материальных ценностей. Анализ данной статьи имеет большое значение для эффективного финансового управления. Запасы могут составлять значительную долю не только оборотных активов, но и активов предприятия в целом. Это может свидетельствовать о том, что предприятия испытывают трудности со сбытом продукции, нарушения технологии производства и выбор неэффективных методов реализации.

Ключевые слова: существенность, политика, финансовая отчетность, упущение, искажение, экономические решения, существенность, достоверность, существенная ошибка, пользователи.

INTRODUCTION

Organization of material accounting is one of the most difficult areas of accounting work. At an industrial enterprise, the range of material assets amounts to tens of thousands of items, and information on inventory accounting accounts for more than 30% of all information on production management. Therefore, the organization of accounting and control over the acquisition, movement, safety and use of material assets is associated with great difficulties. Of great importance is the automation of all accounting work, from issuing accounting documents to drawing up the necessary reports. An integral part of accounting and control of inventories is the economic analysis of their use, which deepens the search for reserves for increasing production efficiency.

Inventories play an important role in the production and economic activities of any enterprise. Inventory and material assets are objects of labor and provide the main production process of the enterprise. Their cost is completely transferred to the newly created product, while occupying a fairly high share.

METHODS

The variety of forms of ownership during the period of a market economy, the expansion of the rights of enterprises in economic management, and the sectoral characteristics of production require alternative, and sometimes multivariate approaches to solving specific issues of methodology and technology for keeping records of industrial inventories.

Basic principles of accounting:

Accrual. Income and expenses are recognized in accounting and reflected in the financial statements of the entity as they are received or incurred, and not on the basis of receipt of funds or payment.

Financial statements are prepared on an accrual basis, under which revenue is recognized (recorded) when it is incurred and when cash is received or paid. According to the accrual principle, it follows, according to the principle of accrual, deferral and distribution to match the income and expenses of the reporting period that may be received as a result of the same or indirectly related transactions or events. In budgetary institutions and entities defined in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which has the force of the Law, "On Accounting," it is allowed to determine income based on the receipt of funds.

Continuity. The subject is considered as continuously operating, that is, as continuing to function in the foreseeable future. It is assumed that it has neither the intention nor the need to liquidate or significantly reduce the scale of its activities.

The entity continues and will continue its activities for an indefinite period of time.

Clarity. The information presented in an entity's financial statements must be understandable to all users.

Significance. Financial information must be meaningful to meet the needs of users in their decision-making process and to help them evaluate business events ^[8].

Materiality. Accounting policies should be designed to disclose information in financial statements that is material if its omission or misrepresentation could affect the economic decisions of users of the financial statements. The significance of information can be influenced by both its essence and its value (materiality).

Credibility. Information is reliable if it is free from material error or bias and can be relied upon by users.

Neutrality. Information presented in financial statements must be free from bias in order to be neutral and reliable.

Prudence. The exercise of caution in making business decisions necessary to make valuations under conditions of uncertainty to ensure that assets and income are not overstated and liabilities or expenses are not overstated.

RESULTS

Enterprises now have the opportunity to choose different ways to organize accounting for the procurement and purchase of materials; reflecting the cost of materials remaining in transit at the end of the month or not removed from suppliers' warehouses; identifying deviations in the actual cost of material assets from accounting prices and their subsequent distribution between materials used in production and their balances in warehouses; repayment of the cost of low-value and rapidly wearing items in use, etc.

DISCUSSION

Managers of enterprises (structural divisions) carrying out production activities must constantly monitor compliance with standards and the dynamics of actual unit costs, since material costs occupy a high proportion of total production costs, and therefore, these costs significantly affect the amount of profit received ^[10]. It follows that saving material resources is the most important factor in increasing production efficiency.

Without proper organization of accounting and control over the use of inventory items, it is impossible to ensure control over balances, receipts and expenditures of inventories in warehouses.

Thus, from the above it follows that this topic is very relevant in a market economy.

A necessary condition for the implementation of plans and the uninterrupted operation of an enterprise in producing products, reducing its cost, increasing profits, and profitability is the complete and timely provision of the enterprise with inventories.

CONCLUSION

Inventories are the most liquid item among the current assets' items. To quickly convert this item into cash, an enterprise must have appropriate services, namely a marketing service – a comprehensive system for organizing product sales aimed at meeting consumer needs based on market research and forecasting. The analysis of this article is of great importance for effective financial management. Inventories can constitute a

significant share not only of current assets, but also of the enterprise's assets in general. This may indicate that enterprises are experiencing difficulties with the sale of products, violations of production technology and the choice of ineffective sales methods. Violation of the optimal level of inventory leads to losses in the activities of enterprises, since it increases the costs of storing these inventories, diverts liquid funds from circulation, increases the risk of depreciation of goods and a decrease in their consumer qualities, and leads to the loss of customers.

References:

1. Alikulov A. (2023). Organizational and methodological bases of accounting the costs of establishing vineyards.
2. Абдиганпарович И. Х., & Юлдашев Ш. Х. (2024). ВОПРОСЫ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ УЧЕТА ЗАТРАТ И СТОИМОСТИ ПРОДУКЦИИ НА СЕЛЬСКОХОЗЯЙСТВЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ. SO 'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI, 7(1), 361-368.
3. Narziyeva G., & Raximova, U. (2023). Superior directions, modern trends and prospects for the development of the financial market.
4. Rabbimovna, R. U., & Farxodovna E. D. (2023). MOLIYA BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USTUVOR YO 'NALISHLARI, ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALARI VA ISTIQBOLLARI. Научный Фокус, 1(7), 709-714.
5. Rabbimovna R. U., Baxtiyrovna N. G., & Muxammadkulovna, Y. D. (2024). AGROKLASTERLARDA TOVAR-MODDIY QIYMATLIKLAR HISOBI VA AUDITINI TAKOMILKASHTIRISH. WORLD OF SCIENCE, 7(3), 140-146.
6. Yorbekova D., & Raximova U. (2023). Modern Foundations of Teaching Economics in University. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 3(2 Part 4), 173-176.
7. Ismatovich A. A. (2023). THEORETICAL BASIS OF ORGANIZING THE ACCOUNT OF COMMODITY MATERIAL ASSETS IN AGROCLUSTERS ON THE BASIS OF INTERNATIONAL StandartS. MASTERS, 1(1), 138-137.
8. Baxodirovich T. J., & Ismatovich A. A. (2023). IMPROVING THE ACCOUNT OF FINANCIAL RESULTS ACCORDING TO INTERNATIONAL StandartS. MASTERS, 1(1), 138-143.
9. Olimjanovna J. D., & Tashmurovich E. U. (2024). CONCEPT AND ACCOUNTING OF CAPITAL INVESTMENTS IN AGRICULTURAL CLUSTERS. JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH, 7(3), 188-188.
10. Ixtiyorovich Q. L. A., Shavkat o'g'li I. R., & Tashmurovich E. U. B. (2023). XARAJATLAR HISOBIDA QO 'LLANILADIGAN ATAMALAR MOHIYATI TAHLILI VA ULARNI TIZIMLASHTIRISH. MASTERS, 1(1), 127-131.
11. Tashmurovich, E. U. (2023). ACCOUNTING AND AUDIT IMPROVEMENT OF READY SALE PRODUCTS IN AGRO-CLUSTER. The Journal of Economics, Finance and Innovation, 649-657.

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Alfraganus universiteti dotsenti, i.f.f.d. (PhD) Fayziyev Oybek Raximovichning umumiy tahriri ostida nashrga tayyorlandi.

O'zbek tili muharriri: Ulug'bek Eshmuradov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Rus tili muharriri: Abdimo'min Alikulov, i.f.d., professor

Musahhih: Xondamir Ismoilov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Bobur Ochilov

2024. Maxsus son

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.

Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

El.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77)

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, [@iqtisodiyot_77](https://t.me/@iqtisodiyot_77) telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Topshirildi: 10.04.2024-yil. Nashrga ruxsat etildi: 19.04.2024-yil.

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va
taraqqiyot” jurnali

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta’lim, fan va innovatsiyalar
vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy
attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-
sonli qarori bilan ro‘yxatdan
o‘tkazilgan.